

Division of Surigao del Sur
MADRID NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics
Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Triachlod: New Formula in Finding the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers

A Mathematics Investigatory Paper Presented to:
Senior High School Faculty

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Division of Surigao del Sur
MADRID NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
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Approval Sheet

This research is entitled as **Triachlod: New Formula for Finding the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers** were formulated and submitted by *Louie Jay M. Estrada, Trisha Mae F. Estal, Kate Angela C. Arienza, Cherilyn E. Sumaoy, and Adrian Dweyne Barlongo* has been approved as the major requirement in Capstone and Research Project subject, specifically in Mathematics Investigatory Project.

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Acknowledgment

This research becomes possible with the accommodating support and help of many people. The researchers would like to extend their sincere thanks to all of the following:

First and foremost, they want to extend this endeavor to Father God Almighty for the knowledge he bestowed upon them, the power, equanimity and for being healthy in order to come-up and finish this study.

They are very grateful to Mr. Algien A. Parker for being their research adviser, for giving them the opportunity to conduct a study and for guidance, as well as for providing essential information regarding this study which helps them to finish their research. Without him this study would not be successful.

They would like to manifest their heartfelt gratitude toward their families for helping them wholeheartedly and for being courageous enough for taking the risks.

Special thanks to their devoted adviser Ms. Ivy M. Maloloy-on for her fruitful advice and especially to Mr. Johnferry P. Sual for helping them most when they needed someone to ask about something important and for helping them how to settle things in research, to Mrs. Jenny Ariate for helping them. To David Dales, who share his time to them, who put efforts for the success of their study.

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To the panel of judges during the final defense; Mrs. Annabel Cubero, Mrs. Mary Grace Maribao and Mrs. Mico Mahinay for giving them their time and for questioning and for having recommendations for the success of their study. Without them they would not realize their mistakes and so.

Their gratefulness and appreciations to their fellow classmates and to the people who had willingly help them throughout their astounding abilities.

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Dedication

The researchers would like to genuinely dedicate this study to the special people behind the success of this study.

To the Father God Almighty who helped and guided them to accomplish their study, to their beloved love ones and friends, to their Alma Mater – Madrid National High School, to their classmates, instructors and to their subject teacher of this subject which is Capstone and Research Project. Without their guidance and support this project would not have been made possible.

The researchers would also like to dedicate this study to their fellow STEM students; they know that this will help them and give them more prolific knowledge.

Abstract

The investigators came up with the study because they wanted to help the students solve the summation of any consecutive odd integers. They wanted to broaden their knowledge in mathematics, specifically in finding the sum of any consecutive odd integers. They wanted to contribute knowledge by deriving a new formula, which can be proven by the Principle of Mathematical Induction.

The investigators derived a new formula in finding the summation of any consecutive odd integers.

$$1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + a_n = \left(\frac{a_n+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1+1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1,$$

where S_n – is the sum of any consecutive odd integers

a_n – is the last given odd term

a_1 – is the first given odd term

Using the said formula, they can find the sum of any consecutive odd integers in a single way.

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CHAPTER I

Background of the Study

In most complex problem in Algebra, finding the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers is hard to find. We have to think first of the given odd numbers, write it down and then compute. Listing down numbers and summing it up is quite mind-blowing and time-consuming. Hence, it is accurate and precise, yet it is time-killing especially when it comes to numbers that are hard to sum-up.

Furthermore, to get the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers of the given numbers, when the given set of numbers are not starting from one, the principal astray to this problem is that we cannot directly get the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers, especially when it involves large numbers. The researchers should have to use the formula $S_n = n \left\{ \frac{2a+(n-1)d}{2} \right\}$ to find the sum of the given problem; nevertheless, they have to find first how many odd numbers are there in the given set of numbers. Subsequently, they can now use $S_n = n \left\{ \frac{2a+(n-1)d}{2} \right\}$ or $S_n = n \left(\frac{a_1+a_n}{2} \right)$ to find the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers in the given problem. (Retrieved from: <https://schooltutoring.com/help/review-of-arithmetic-series/>)

This study involves an appropriate way of building mental discipline and encourages logical reasoning and mental rigor. Although, it is one of the most difficult branches of mathematics yet it brings a feeling of euphoria to people who find it hard to deal with this kind of problem. There are lots of students struggling

in solving Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers particularly if it involves problem that is difficult to solve.

Answering this kind of problem, most especially when the given problem is large enough to count or even write down should be exact and at the same time amusing to stay still with the given problem. In coherence, the researchers want to give assistance to students who struggle to solve this kind of problem for them to attain an exact answer in a short span of time by finding a short-cut formula in solving the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to help easily find the answers to the problems relating to the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers. Specifically, the purposes of this study are as follows:

1. To find another formula in finding the summation of any consecutive odd integers.
2. To prove Triachlod Formula using the Principle of Mathematical Induction.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant to the following:

Students – It will help students solve such mathematical problem into one way process and this will improve their knowledge prolifically.

Teachers – This is beneficial to teachers who aim to engage students in solving logical mathematical problems relating to Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers.

School – It can help achieve progressive development through the students and teachers' influential intellect excellence making the school acquire a good background status.

Future researchers – This study will encourage the future researchers to discover new ideas and facts that will help them improve due to its uniqueness and useful contents.

Scope and Limitations

This study is only limited to the use of short-cut formula of Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers. It is conducted inside the vicinity area of Madrid National High School. The whole study will cover the second semester of the School Year 2019-2020. The researchers will make a further investigation about the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers.

Definition of Terms

Mental Discipline - The practice of engaging one's intellectual capacity involving solving mathematical problems such as equations, summations and whatnot.

$S_n = n \left(\frac{2a_1 + (n-1)d}{2} \right)$ - Formula in finding the summation of any consecutive numbers. It needs the number of numbers in the given problem to solve for the summation.

Summation - The total or sum of series of numbers presented in the given problem.

Triachlod - is the combination of names of the researchers; namely, Trisha, Angela, Cherilyn, Louie and Dweyne.

Triachlod Formula - $S_n = \left(\frac{a_n+1}{2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1+1}{2} \right)^2 + a_1$; it is the derived formula for the summation of any consecutive odd integers.

CHAPTER II

Review of Related Literature

This chapter presents a review of relevant literature and study pertinent to the success of the investigation.

Foreign Literatures

According to Barile (2020), Sigma is represented as the eighteenth (18) letter of the ancient Greek alphabet. It is used as a symbol for summation and series.

As what Weisstein (2020) stated, Friedrich Gauss, a German mathematician contributed in the field of Algebra. Summation is one of his contributions in the field of mathematics and is known as the arithmetic series.

The term is computed from the previous number in which the number should be added or subtracted by a constant d . When $k > 1$; the formula would be;

$$a_k = a_{k-1} + d = a_{k-2} + 2d = \dots = a_1 + d(k-1)$$

The summands of the series of the n numbers is then listed on the following given which would be;

$$S_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k$$

$$S_n = \sum_{k=1}^n (a_1 + (k-1)d)$$

$$S_n = n a_1 + d \sum_{k=1}^n (k - 1)$$

$$S_n = n a_1 + d \sum_{k=2}^n (k - 1)$$

$$S_n = n a_1 + d \sum_{k=1}^n k$$

Using the identity for summation of numbers;

$$\sum_{k=1}^n k = \frac{1}{2}n(n + 1)$$

Then, after the process of deriving the summation series, the formula would be;

$$S_n = n a_1 - 1 + d = a_k - 2 + 2d = \dots = a_1 + d (k - 1)$$

Put in mind that;

$$a_1 + a_n = a_1 + \{a_1 + d (n - 1)\} = 2a_1 + d (n - 1)$$

The resulting formula would be;

$$S_n = \frac{1}{2}n (a_1 + a_n)$$

This is derived by Gauss, when he was still young and his teacher asked him to solve the problem of summing up numbers from 1 to 100.

In this case, the abovementioned formula can be expressed in a specific process of solving. The accurateness of its pattern when summing up numbers that is consecutive and in which it starts from 1 is very visible.

According to Weisstein (2020), Geometric series is a series of numbers in which the ratio of each two consecutive terms $\frac{a_{k+1}}{a_k}$ is represented as the constant function of the summation index k . For the simplest case of the ratio $r = \frac{a_{k+1}}{a_k}$, the terms a_k are formed as $a_k = a_0 r^k$. In which $a_0 = 1$; its constant is represented as $|r| < 1$.

It could be processed as;

$$S_n = \sum_{k=0}^n a_k = \sum_{k=0}^n r^k$$

This could then be;

$$S_n = \sum_{k=0}^n r^k = 1 + r + r^2 + \dots + r^n$$

Multiplying both sides by r ;

$$r(S_n = r + r^2 + r^3 + \dots + r^{n+1})$$

Subtracting $(1 + r + r^2 + \dots + r^n)$ from $(r + r^2 + r^3 + \dots + r^{n+1})$;

$$\begin{aligned}(1-r) S_n &= (1 + r + r^2 + \dots + r^n) - (r + r^2 + r^3 + \dots + r^{n+1}) \\ &= 1 - r^{n+1}\end{aligned}$$

The result would be;

$$S_n = \sum_{k=0}^n r^k = \frac{1}{1-r}$$

It is similar when the sums are gotten starting at $k = 1$ instead of $k = 0$;

$$\sum_{k=1}^n r^k = \frac{r(1-r^n)}{1-r}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} r^k = \frac{r}{1-r}$$

In which it is valid for $|r| < 1$.

CHAPTER III

Research Methodology

This chapter presents; the conceptual framework, materials being used, general process, about the formula, rules of using the formula, research design, locale, respondents, instrument and procedures.

Conceptual Framework

This study is focused on finding the summation of any consecutive odd integers. The illustration below is the conceptual framework of the study.

Materials

- Paper
- Pen
- Calculator

General Process

Finding the short-cut formula of the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers.

The investigators came-up with their first formula, but the sad thing was it was already on the internet, so as their second attempt, and luckily on their third attempt they did not fail. They used different operations to come-up with the new formula of the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers. They then listed the odd numbers starting from 1 for testing, listed the difference and the total of numbers.

They got the pattern which is the square of any natural numbers which is represented as the number of odd numbers in the given problem to the 2nd power. The mentioned is applicable only to the summation series of odd integers starting from 1.

After getting the pattern which is already on the internet, they try again and dig more and more information to get another hint. They come-up with $n = \frac{a_n + 1}{2}$ which is to find the number of terms in the given problem starting from 1, where a_n represents the last term of the given problem. Then, they have found formulas for finding the number of numbers present in the given set of numbers in the given problem; which are $n = \frac{a_n - a_1}{2} + 1$; where a_n and a_1 are odd numbers, $n =$

$\frac{a_n - a_1}{2}$; where a_n and a_1 are even numbers; which means that the even numbers are not counted in the summation, and $n = \frac{a_n - a_1 + 1}{2}$; where a_n and a_1 is either odd and even in pair or even and odd in pair. The term a_1 represents the first term of the given set of numbers, while a_n represents the last term of the given set of numbers.

About the New Formula

Triachlod Formula which is $S_n = \left(\frac{a_n+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1+1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$; where a_n is the last term, a_1 is the first term, and S_n is the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Numbers. This formula comes from combining the abovementioned formulas which the investigators had invented. The n^2 formula is the major basis as to how the researchers come-up with the new formula $S_n = \left(\frac{a_n+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1+1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$.

As perceived from the Triachlod Formula: a_n and a_1 are both added by 1, it is because of the problem that is odd; for the resulting answer, which is even to be divided by 2. Then $\frac{a_n+1}{2}$ and $\frac{a_1+1}{2}$ are both squared. The summation of odd integers from the first term is then subtracted to the summation of odd numbers from the last term for its partial summation. Lastly, the first term is added to find the resulting summation of any consecutive odd integers.

Rules

1. Note that adding the first number and subtracting the second number and so on or solving with alternating operations (+1, -3, +4 and so on) of any series of consecutive odd numbers is the exception of using the formula.

2. Substitute the given first term and the last term (should be odd numbers) of any consecutive odd series problem to the Triachlod Formula and simplify to arrive a precise answer.

3. If the given a_n and a_1 are both negative (-); emit the negative sign and substitute to the formula, then make the resulting summation negative.

5. Can be substituted with large numbers and so on.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents; proving the formula using Mathematical Induction to prove the study.

Using the Principle of Mathematical Induction, prove that;

$$1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + a_n = \left(\frac{a_n+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1+1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1;$$

where $a_1 = 1$

where $a_n = 1$

Is true for all positive odd integers.

I. Prove that the identity is true for $n = 1$

The equation below consists of three terms equal to 1; $a_n = a_1 = 1$.

$$1 = \left(\frac{a_n + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

$$1 = \left(\frac{1+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{1+1}{2}\right)^2 + 1$$

$$1 = \left(\frac{2}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{2}\right)^2 + 1$$

$$1 = (1)^2 - (1)^2 + 1$$

$$1 = 1 - 1 + 1$$

$$1 = 1$$

II. Assume that the formula is true for $n = k$, that is:

$$1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + a_k = \left(\frac{a_k+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1+1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

We want to show that the formula is true for $a_n = a_k + 2$;

That is:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + a_k + (a_k + 2) &= \left(\frac{a_k+2+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{1+1}{2}\right)^2 + 1 \\ \text{(Simplify the fractions)} &= \left(\frac{a_k+3}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{2}\right)^2 + 1 \\ &= \left(\frac{a_k + 3}{2}\right)^2 - (1)^2 + 1 \\ &= \left(\frac{a_k+3}{2}\right)^2 - 1 + 1 \\ &= \left(\frac{a_k+3}{2}\right)^2 \text{ or } \frac{a_k^2+6a_k+9}{4} \end{aligned}$$

Proof:

To get the sum of the first $a_k + 2$ integers we must add up all the positive odd integers from 1 to a_k and then add on $a_k + 2$, since the sum of the first $a_k + 2$ integers is:

$$1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + a_k + (a_k + 2)$$

Now, we must use our assumption. Remember that we are assuming that;

$$1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + a_k = \left(\frac{a_k+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1+1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

So we can substitute;

$$\left(\frac{a_k + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

For $1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + a_k$ in our expression above for the sum of the first $a_k + 2$ positive odd integers. Now we have the sum of the first $a_k + 2$ positive odd integers is;

$$\left(\frac{a_k + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1 + (a_k + 2)$$

Remember that we are trying to show that the sum of the first $a_k + 2$ positive odd integers is:

Assume that $a_1 = 1$; the 2nd and the 3rd term will be omitted.

$$\left(\frac{a_k+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1+1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1 + (a_k + 2)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k^2+2a_k+1}{4}\right) - \left(\frac{1+1}{2}\right)^2 + 1 + (a_k + 2)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k^2+2a_k+1}{4}\right) - \left(\frac{2}{2}\right)^2 + 1 + (a_k + 2)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k^2+2a_k+1}{4}\right) - (1)^2 + 1 + (a_k + 2)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k^2+2a_k+1}{4}\right) - 1 + 1 + (a_k + 2)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k^2+2a_k+1}{4}\right) + (a_k + 2)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k^2+2a_k+1+4a_k+8}{4}\right)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k^2+2a_k+4a_k+1+8}{4}\right)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k^2 + 6a_k + 9}{4}\right)$$

$$\left(\frac{a_k + 3}{2}\right)^2$$

The term $\left(\frac{a_k + 3}{2}\right)^2$ is the same as $\frac{a_k^2 + 6a_k + 9}{4}$.

We have shown that the formula for the sum of the first a_n positive odd integers is true for $a_n = 1$. We have also shown that whenever it is true for $a_n = a_k$; it is also true for $a_n = a_k + 2$. Since we know it is true for $a_n = 1$. It must therefore be true for $a_n = 3$. Similarly, since it is true for $a_n = 3$, it must therefore be true for $a_n = 5$, and it must therefore be true for $a_n = 7, \dots$

It has proven that the sum of the first a_n positive odd integers of $\left(\frac{a_n + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$ is true for all positive odd integer values for the sum of a_n .

CHAPTER V

FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents; findings, conclusion and recommendation of the study

Findings

- The answer of the problem of the Triachlod Formula was proved to be accurate.
- Triachlod Formula can now be used in problems related to Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers.

Conclusion

- Calculating the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers using the Triachlod Formula is very accurate.
- Triachlod Formula is very helpful in problems related to finding the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers.
- It is a very helpful learning tool to improve the critical thinking skills of the students and mental rigor.

Recommendation

- Based from the findings and conclusions of the study, further studies must and should be conducted to validate the use of the new found formula which can be used in another kind of summation.

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Appendices

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Appendix A

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Appendix B

Letter of Approval

Letter to the Validators

Letter to the Respondents

Division of Surigao del Sur
MADRID NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics
Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Letter of Approval

January 06, 2020
CORSINO M. GALELA JR.
Secondary School Principal III
Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Dear Sir,

Greetings from the researchers,

We the grade 12 – STEM researchers from Madrid National High School are presently conducting research study entitled as “**Triachlod: New Formula in Finding the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers.**” The subject respondents of the study are the Junior High School Mathematics Teachers. This covers the School Year 2019-2020.

Regarding this matter, we would like to ask permission for having this kind of study inside the vicinity area of Madrid National High School. The researchers will provide survey questionnaires considering the confidentiality of students’ responses. We are anticipating a positive response and approval for this earnest- request.

Thank you very much, God bless and more power.

Respectfully yours,

KATE ANGELA ARIENZA

LOUIE JAY ESTRADA

TRISHA MAE ESTAL

CHERILYN SUMAOY

ADRIAN DWEYNE BARLONGO
Researchers

CORSINO M. GALELA JR.
Secondary School Principal III

Division of Surigao del Sur
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Letter to the Validators

January 24, 2020
JHS/SHS Faculty
Madrid National High School
Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Dear Ma'am/Sir:

Warmest greetings!

The undersigned are students of STEM strand presently conducting a Mathematics Investigatory Project entitled "***Triachlod: New Formula in Finding the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers***" as one of the requirements in the subject Capstone and Research Project.

In this connection, may we request you to validate our survey questionnaire and enhance the contents if necessary. This is to ensure that it could draw significant outcome as intended for this study.

Attached to this letter are the survey questionnaire and the evaluation tool for your perusals.

Your favorable consideration on this regard is highly appreciated.

Respectfully yours,

(SGD) KATE ANGELA ARIENZA
(SGD) LOUIE JAY ESTRADA
(SGD) TRISHA MAE ESTAL
(SGD) CHERILYN SUMAOY
(SGD) ADRIAN DWEYNE BARLONGO
Researchers

Signature over Printed Name

Division of Surigao del Sur
MADRID NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics
Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Letter to the Respondents

January 24, 2020

Dear respondents,

Greetings from the researchers,

We the grade 12 – STEM researchers from Madrid National High School would like to invite you to participate in our research study entitled as **Triachlod: New Formula in Finding the Summation of any Consecutive Odd Integers.**

Your participation and cooperation in this study is wholeheartedly needed. It would be of great pleasure if you will voluntarily agree to be one of our respondents during your free time. We would like you to test the new formula that we have derived and be the first to use the formula.

Thank you so much for accepting our invitation. We will look forward for your appearance. God bless you so much.

Yours very truly,

The Researchers

ALGIEN A. PARKER

Research Adviser

ANNABEL C. CUBERO

Senior High School Coordinator

CORSINO M. GALELA JR.

Secondary School Principal III

Appendix C
Survey Questionnaire

Name: _____ **Grade Level of Math Teachers:** _____

Criteria for the Triachlod Formula

Direction: After testing the Triachlod Formula that the researchers have provided. Put a check () on the table below **YES**, if the answer coming from the Triachlod Formula is correct and **NO** if it is not.

Is the desired level of accuracy exact?

Perception	Triachlod Formula	
	YES	NO
a. The answer is correct		

Signature over Printed Name

Appendix D

Samples of the Accurateness of the Derived Formula

Triachlod Formula

The researchers have provided samples using the Triachlod Formula and have compared the answers to the Summation Series Formula.

1. The sum of odd numbers from 1 to 99.

First, they have to write the Triachlod Formula which would be represented as:

$$S_n = \left(\frac{a_n + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

Substituting the given numbers from Triachlod Formula; they have,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{99 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

Simplifying; they have,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{100}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{2}\right)^2 + 1$$

$$S_n = (50)^2 - (1)^2 + 1$$

$$S_n = 2,500 - 1 + 1$$

$$\mathbf{S_n = 2,500}$$

2. The sum of odd numbers from 1 to 4,999.

They have to repeat the process; write the Triachlod Formula which would be,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{a_n + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

Substituting the given numbers from Triachlod Formula; they have,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{4,999 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + 1$$

Simplifying; they have,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{5,000}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{2}\right)^2 + 1$$

$$S_n = (2,500)^2 - (1)^2 + 1$$

$$S_n = 6,250,000 - 1 + 1$$

$$\mathbf{S_n = 6,250,000}$$

3. The sum of odd numbers from 549 to 9,659.

Again, they have to write the Triachlod Formula which would be represented as:

$$S_n = \left(\frac{a_n + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

Substituting the given numbers from Triachlod Formula; they have,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{9,659 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{549 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + 549$$

Simplifying; they have,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{9,660}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{550}{2}\right)^2 + 549$$

$$S_n = (4,830)^2 - (275)^2 + 549$$

$$S_n = 23,328,900 - 75625 + 549$$

$$S_n = 23,328,900 - 75076$$

$$S_n = \mathbf{23,253,824}$$

4. The sum of odd numbers from 1,353 to 91,827.

Again, they have to write the Triachlod Formula which would be represented as:

$$S_n = \left(\frac{a_n + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_1 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + a_1$$

Substituting the given numbers from Triachlod Formula; they have,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{91,827 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{1,353 + 1}{2}\right)^2 + 1,353$$

Simplifying; they have,

$$S_n = \left(\frac{91,828}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{1,354}{2}\right)^2 + 1,353$$

$$S_n = (45,914)^2 - (677)^2 + 1,353$$

$$S_n = 2,108,095,396 - 458,329 + 1,353$$

$$S_n = 2,108,095,396 - 456,976$$

$$S_n = \mathbf{2,107,638,420}$$

Comparing the answers of Triachlod Formula to Summation Series Formula

The Summation Series Formula would be represented as;

$$S_n = n \left(\frac{2a_1 + (n-1)d}{2} \right)$$

1. The sum of odd numbers from 1 to 99.

But before they could substitute the given numbers to the given formula, they have to find first the number of odd numbers. They have to use the formula that they have derived;

$$n = \frac{a_n - a_1}{d} + 1$$

Substituting they have;

$$n = \frac{99 - 1}{2} + 1$$

$$n = \frac{98}{2} + 1$$

$$n = 49 + 1$$

$$n = 50$$

Substituting the number of terms and the numbers from the given problem to the Summation Series Formula; they have,

$$S_n = n \left(\frac{2a_1 + (n-1)d}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 50 \left(\frac{2(1) + (50-1)2}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 50 \left(\frac{2 + (49)2}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 50 \left(\frac{2 + 98}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 50 \left(\frac{100}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 50(50)$$

$$\checkmark S_n = 2,500$$

2. The sum of odd numbers from 1 to 4,999.

They have to repeat the process; they have to use the formula that they have derived;

$$n = \frac{a_n - a_1}{2} + 1$$

Substituting they have;

$$n = \frac{4,999 - 1}{2} + 1$$

$$n = \frac{4,998}{2} + 1$$

$$n = 2499 + 1$$

Substituting the number of terms and the numbers from the given problem to the formula below; they have,

$$S_n = n \left(\frac{2a_1 + (n - 1)2}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 2,500 \left(\frac{2(1) + (2,500 - 1)2}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 2,500 \left(\frac{2 + (2,499)2}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 2,500 \left(\frac{2 + 4,998}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 2,500 \left(\frac{5,000}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 2,500(2,500)$$

$$S_n = 50(50)$$

$$\checkmark S_n = 6,250,000$$

3. The sum of odd numbers from 549 to 9,659.

This is more complicated than the problem in number 1 and 2.

$$n = \frac{a_n - a_1}{2} + 1$$

Substituting the given above to the formula in finding the number of odd terms from 549 to 9,659; they have,

$$n = \frac{9,659 - 549}{2} + 1$$

$$n = \frac{9,110}{2} + 1$$

$$n = 4,555 + 1$$

$$n = 4,556$$

Substituting the number of odd terms and the numbers from the given problem to the formula listed below; they have,

$$S_n = n \left(\frac{2a_1 + (n-1)d}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 4,556 \left(\frac{2(549) + (4,556-1)d}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 4,556 \left(\frac{1,098 + (4,555)d}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 4,556 \left(\frac{1,098 + 9110}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 4,556 \left(\frac{10,208}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 4,556(5,104)$$

$$\checkmark S_n = 23,253,824$$

4. The sum of odd numbers from 1,353 to 91,827.

This is way more complicated than the problem in number 3. They have to use the formula listed below to find the number of terms within odd numbers from 1,353 to 91,827.

$$n = \frac{a_n - a_1}{2} + 1$$

Substituting the given above to the formula in finding the number of odd terms from 1,353 to 91,827 they have,

$$n = \frac{91,827 - 1,353}{2} + 1$$

$$n = \frac{90,474}{2} + 1$$

$$n = 45,237 + 1$$

$$n = 45,238$$

Substituting the number of odd terms and the numbers from the given problem to the formula below; they have,

$$S_n = n \left(\frac{2a_1 + (n-1)d}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 45,238 \left(\frac{2(1,353) + (45,238-1)d}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 45,238 \left(\frac{183,654 + (45,237)d}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 45,238 \left(\frac{2,706 + 90,474}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 45,238 \left(\frac{93,180}{2} \right)$$

$$S_n = 45,238(46,590)$$

$$\checkmark S_n = 2,107,638,420$$

Appendix E

Documentation

Researchers conducting a survey to Mathematics Teachers

Appendix F

Curriculum Vitae

Name: Adrian Dweyne Bato Barlongo

Sex: Male

Status: Single

Age: 17

Phone Number: 09459862099

Grade/ Strand: 12 – STEM

Email Address: adrianbarlongo02@gmail.com

Place of Birth: OLPHI Hospital, Barangay San Policarpo, Calbayog City, Samar

Current Address: Purok 8, Barangay Quirino, Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Skills: Active Listening, Vocal Impersonating, Good Housekeeping, Self-teaching and Learning through Experiences.

Hobbies: I always spend my time doing household chores given by my mother, and then I involve myself to social media afterwards.

Educational Attainment/ Awards:

- **Secondary Level**
 - Senior High School
 - Academic awardee
 - Junior High School
 - Graduated Junior High School
 - Academic Awardee during Grade 10
 - STE qualifier student in Grade 7-8.
- **Elementary**
 - Elementary Graduate

Objective/s of making the study:

Nurturing academic knowledge about mathematics through this study will help student not just to make the problem easier, but also to encourage them to discover new equations or other mathematical discoveries.

Inspiration in making the study:

I was influenced by my sister (Civil Engineering) that is good in mathematics. She tends to tease me when I find it hard to solve using addition and subtraction in my old school days. As time goes by, teasing makes me pursue to study hard and enlighten my pride that I can be as good as her.

Grade-10 General Average in Mathematics: 92

Name: Louie Jay Magsanay Estrada

Sex: Male

Status: Single

Age: 19

Phone Number: 09101375673

Grade/ Strand: 12 – STEM

Email Address: Ljestrade123@gmail.com

Place of Birth: Pangubatan, Kaputian, Island Garden City of Samal, Davao Norte

Current Address: Purok 1, Barangay Quirino, Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Skills: Listening, Communication, Computer Skills, Observation, and Studying

Hobbies: I love to read books, explore something new to me, derive a formula or something, watch movies, and discover something new. I love to play Volleyball.

Educational Attainment/ Awards:

- **Secondary Level**

Senior High School

- Academic Awardee
- Photojournalism (Collaborative Desktop Publishing – Division Qualifier)
- Regional Chess Qualifier (PRISAA)

Junior High School

- Graduated as 4th Honor
- Grade 7 – 10 Class Valedictorian
- Academic Awardee during Grade 8 – 9
- Siliman University, Honor Certificate

- **Elementary**

- Elementary Graduate
- Honor Student in Grade – III

Objective/s of making the study:

Learning more in the field of Mathematics is a gift. It is good to explore more about math in order to achieve something achievable. Mathematics is not hard at all; all you have to do is to exert effort and patience to learn. Embrace it and you will know the uniqueness hidden behind it.

Inspiration in making the study:

All of my sufferings lead me in pursuing something achievable. They made it hard for me to take the challenge every time I face them, yet I still think outside the box. This is because I believe that “Suffering sucks, but suffering is the foundation of success.”

Grade-10 General Average in Mathematics: 95

Name: Kate Angela Cubillan Arienza

Sex: Female

Status: Single

Age: 18

Phone Number: 09153570022

Grade/ Strand: 12 – STEM

Email Address: Kateangelaarienza@gmail.com

Place of Birth: Sta. Ana Manila

Current Address: Purok 1, Barangay Linibunan, Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Skills: Cooker and Active listening

Hobbies: I love watching movies, singing, dancing and to tour around

Educational Attainment/ Awards:

- **Secondary Level**
 - Senior High School
 - Academic Awardee
 - Junior High School
 - Graduated as Academic Awardee
- **Elementary**
 - Elementary Graduate
 - Grade II, Academic Awardee

Objective/s of making the study:

To widen intellectual ability of individuals who have difficulties in finding consecutive odd integers and to gain more knowledge related to this topic.

Inspiration in making the study:

One of my inspirations in doing this study is my co-members because of their determination, hard works, perseverance and eagerness of success mindset.

Grade-10 General Average in Mathematics: 93

Name: Trisha Mae Fallado Estal

Sex: Female

Status: Single

Age: 17

Phone Number: 09098359148

Grade/ Strand: 12 – STEM

Email Address: Aerishkwatro@gmail.com

Place of Birth: Antao Carmen Surigao del Sur

Current Address: Purok-2, Antao, Carmen, Surigao del Sur

Skills: cooking

Hobbies: I love playing Volleyball, reading Wattpad, books, travelling and discovering new recipes

Educational Attainment/ Awards:

- **Secondary Level**
 - Senior High School
 - Academic awardee
 - Junior High School
 - Academic Awardee during Grade 8 – 9
- **Elementary**
 - Elementary Graduate
 - Grade 1 – 6 honor student

Objective/s of making the study:

To be able to cope-up and widen the knowledge about summation of any consecutive odd integers. To encourage everyone to explore math even more.

Inspiration in making the study:

Somehow I dislike math, so I want something new or a new way that can be understood by every one of us. That is why we take the risk of exploring mathematics, because it is fun.

Grade-10 General Average in Mathematics: 91

Name: Cherilyn Eyana Sumaoy

Sex: Female

Status: Single

Age: 18

Phone Number: 09300451970

Grade/ Strand: 12 – STEM

Email Address: sumaoycherilyn@gmail.com

Place of Birth: Bayogo, Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Current Address: Purok – 2 Brgy. Bayogo, Madrid, Surigao del Sur

Skills: Active Listening, Communication, and Studying

Hobbies: I love to read books, watching movies, explore something new, and to tour around.

Educational Attainment/ Awards:

- **Secondary Level**
 - Senior High School
 - Academic awardee
 - Junior High School
 - Graduated Junior High School
 - Academic Awardee during Grade - 10
 - STE qualifier student in Grade 7 - 10.
- **Elementary**
 - Elementary Graduate
 - 3rd Honor in Grade III

Objective/s of making the study:

To be able to learn and know more about Mathematics is my goal. It is good to explore more about math in order to achieve something achievable.

Inspiration in making the study:

I want to contribute something in Mathematics. I know that it is hard, but still I want to overcome every hurdle in Mathematics.

Grade-10 General Average in Mathematics: 91